

ROAD FEATURES ENHANCEMENT IN SENTINEL-2 IMAGERY USING CONDITIONAL DILATION AND LINEAR STRUCTURING ELEMENTS

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RESUMO – O presente estudo avaliou a aplicação do operador de dilatação condicional e sua variante baseada em erosão para aprimorar as linhas centrais de estradas em imagens multiespectrais Sentinel-2. A análise envolveu várias bandas espectrais (b2, b3, b4, b8) e índices derivados (NDVI, NDBI, NDWI), usando um conjunto de dados de aproximadamente 890 recortes de imagem por banda. Os resultados demonstraram que um comprimento de elemento estruturante de 380 pixels proporcionou a melhor compensação na maioria das bandas, embora não tenham sido observadas melhorias significativas na banda b4. O operador de dilatação condicional ($\delta_{B,X}$) obteve bons resultados nas bandas NDBI e NDWI, enquanto o operador variante ($\delta'_{B,X}$) teve melhor desempenho para b8 e NDVI. O uso do operador de abertura por reconstrução como uma etapa de pré-processamento teve influência limitada no desempenho da segmentação e, em alguns casos, degradou sutilmente os resultados. Pesquisas futuras devem explorar definições de marcadores mais seletivas para reconstrução e combinar várias estratégias morfológicas para melhorar a robustez da segmentação de estradas.

ABSTRACT – This study evaluated the application of the conditional dilation operator, and its erosion-based variant, for enhancing road centerlines in Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery. The analysis involved multiple spectral bands (b2, b3, b4, b8) and derived indices (NDVI, NDBI, NDWI), using a dataset of approximately 890 image patches per band. Results demonstrated that a structuring element length of 380 pixels provided the best trade-off across most bands, although no significant improvements were observed for band b4. The conditional dilation operator ($\delta_{B,X}$) achieved strong results in NDBI and NDWI bands, while the variant operator ($\delta'_{B,X}$) performed better for b8 and NDVI. The use of the opening-by-reconstruction operator as a preprocessing step had limited influence on segmentation performance, and in some cases, subtly degraded results. Future research should explore more selective marker definitions for reconstruction and combine multiple morphological strategies to improve road segmentation robustness.

1 INTRODUCTION

The objective of this study is to present the results of experiments using conditional dilation operator, from Mathematical Morphology, to enhance road features in satellite images.

The rapid urban expansion observed in recent decades has led to significant development of road networks. This continuously evolving infrastructure requires frequent updates to existing road maps (CORENTIN *et al.*, 2018). As essential elements within the class of topographic objects, roads must be consistently updated in cartographic databases to support emergency response operations, facilitate automated navigation systems, assist urban planning, and enhance traffic management systems (ABDOLLAHI *et al.*, 2020).

Accurate and up-to-date maps are particularly crucial given the widespread use of location-based services and the imminent arrival of autonomous vehicles. However, updating these maps remains both costly and labor-intensive. Several companies have invested hundreds of millions of dollars in global road mapping, yet in spite of these investments, data error rates remain high (BASTANI *et al.*, 2018).

For object segmentation in images, of which road segmentation is a specific case, machine learning-based approaches are becoming increasingly prevalent, with a growing emphasis on deep learning models. In this context, many road segmentation methods based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) have demonstrated strong performance on public remote sensing datasets (CHENG et al, 2017).

The increasing number of studies on road segmentation has led to specialization over time. Depending on the intended application, various road extraction methods have been proposed in recent years (ZHANG et al. 2020). The diversity of techniques and methodologies employed in road segmentation research is so extensive that no clear consensus exists within the scientific community regarding a standardized classification of these approaches.

Regardless of the variety of methods applied in road segmentation, it is evident that machine learning (ML) techniques occupy a prominent position in remote sensing research. These techniques encompass the most advanced tools currently available for semantic segmentation and object detection tasks.

In this context, despite the undeniable advances of deep learning-based techniques for road segmentation, certain properties of more traditional approaches can still be effectively integrated with state-of-the-art machine learning (ML) methods. Among these conventional techniques, Mathematical Morphology (MM) operators stand out, having been employed in various remote sensing image segmentation tasks.

The studies conducted by Gao et al. (2019), Lian and Huang. (2019) and Zao et al. (2022) illustrate that methodologies incorporating explicit modeling of geometric attributes can provide auxiliary features that enhance the performance of state-of-the-art neural network models or even accelerate their training. Thus, despite the unquestionable dominance of neural network-based techniques in semantic segmentation tasks, the use of traditional methods should not be disregarded, as they have the potential to further improve the efficiency of contemporary deep learning models.

Based on these considerations, this study conducted experiments using the conditional dilation morphological operator on Sentinel-2 satellite imagery, aiming to evaluate its effectiveness in the task of road segmentation.

The following sections describe the general aspects of the experiment. Section 2 details the methodology, including materials, methods, and the data used. Section 3 covers the experiments, results and a brief discussion. Section 4 summarizes the study and outlines potential directions for future research.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Mathematical morphology operators

Mathematical morphology (MM) is used for the analysis of spatial structures in images and is primarily based on the shape of objects within a scene. Morphological operators do not prioritize gray-level values; instead, they rely on specific geometric characteristics of objects in the image. Mathematical morphology can be applied to any image processing domain in which object shape plays a significant role (LEDDA, 2007).

Mathematical Morphology studies the decomposition of operators between complete lattices in terms of four classes of operators: dilations, erosions, anti-dilations, and anti-erosions. These operators, referred to as elementary, play a fundamental role, as any other operator can be constructed from them (BANON and BARREIRA, 1998).

In the present experiment, the n-conditional dilation operator with structuring elements in four distinct profiles was applied to Sentinel-2 images. The n-conditional dilation for binary images is defined as successive applications (n) of the conditional dilation (or geodesic) operator ($\delta_{B,X}$):

$$\delta_{B,X}^n(Y) = (\delta_{B,X}(Y))^n = (\delta_B(Y) \cap X)^n \quad (1)$$

Where $\delta_B(Y)$ is the dilation of a subset Y of the image, used as a initial reference (marker), by a structuring element B , and X is a subset of the image A . It should be noted that when the markers Y are equal to X , and n equals 1 , the operation corresponds to a dilation.

A variant of the n-conditional dilation operator ($\delta_{B,X}$) was used on the same set of images, applying the erosion operator instead of dilation. This operator was named as $\delta'_{B,X}$.

The implementation of the morphological operators and the experiments described in this work were carried out using the *OpenCV*, *SKimage* libraries in the Python programming language. The experiments aimed to evaluate the effects of conditional dilation on Sentinel-2 bands under different configurations, as well as the influence of structuring elements of varying lengths on the final results.

The routine also computes the metrics by comparing the binarized images with their corresponding masks, generating visualizations such as boxplots and bar charts for comparative analysis across spectral bands and techniques. The focus is on the quantitative and visual comparison of the enhancement methods effectiveness in separating linear structures, such as roads, from spectral bands.

All routines were implemented in the collaborative environment *Kaggle*, and are available at: <https://www.kaggle.com/code/danielwander/simgeo-2025-article-mm-experiments>.

2.2 Dataset

For the experiment, image tiles were extracted from eight Sentinel-2 scenes encompassing portions of the states of São Paulo (SP), Minas Gerais (MG), and Rio de Janeiro (RJ), as illustrated in Figure 1. To guide the tile extraction, OpenStreetMap vector data corresponding to paved roads were compiled to generate binary masks representing road centerlines.

Figure 1 - Sentinel-2 images used for the creation of the dataset, covering portions of the states of São Paulo (SP), Minas Gerais (MG), and Rio de Janeiro (RJ).

For the dataset generation, Sentinel-2 bands b2, b3, b4, and b8 were exported to the .tif format using the SNAP software (version 9.0.0). From the combination of these Sentinel-2 bands, additional layers were derived using the NDVI, NDBI, and NDWI spectral indices. Thus, considering the three index-derived images together with the four original bands, the final dataset consisted of eight bands, each with approximately 890 samples.

2.3 Evaluation metrics

The results of applying conditional dilation operators to the Sentinel-2 images consist of binary images highlighting the features of interest, as shown in Figure 7. Given the availability of binary masks corresponding to the roads present in the images, it was possible to compute performance indicators for the applied morphological operators. This evaluation was carried out by comparing the pixel values of the binary images resulting from the application of mathematical morphology operators with the corresponding pixels in the ground-truth mask images.

Accordingly, to quantitatively assess the resulting binary images, the Intersection over Union (IoU) and F1-Score metrics were employed, following the methodology used by Chen et al. (2023):

$$IoU = \frac{TP}{(TP + FP + FN)} \quad (2)$$

$$F1 - Score = \frac{2 \cdot TP}{(2 \cdot TP + FP + FN)} \quad (3)$$

Where *TP* (True Positives) refers to positive pixels correctly classified as positive, *FP* (False Positives) refers to negative pixels incorrectly classified as positive, *TN* (True Negatives) refers to negative pixels correctly classified as negative, and *FN* (False Negatives) refers to positive pixels incorrectly classified as negative.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Testing procedure

The routine for n -conditional dilation in the experiment involved applying dilation operator ($\delta_{B,X}$) to a band, with a linear structuring element covering four different profiles (0° , 45° , 90° and 135°), followed by a comparison between the results of this operation and the original images, preserving only the invariant pixels. A variant of conditional dilation ($\delta'_{B,X}$) included in the tests was the application of the erosion operator, instead of dilation, with the aim of enhancing the road axes that appear darker in certain spectral bands.

Another morphological operator used in the experiments was the opening by reconstruction, implemented using the *reconstruction* module from the Python library *skimage*. For the marker composition, the image resulting from the erosion operator (E) was used as start pint ($R^0 = E$) was used. Starting from the marker, the eroded image is reconstructed using the original image A as a reference, through an iterative process that continues until convergence after k iterations. The opening by reconstruction for binary images is defined by Banon and Barreira (1998) as an iterative process:

$$\gamma_{B,Y}(X) = U_{n=1,\dots} \delta_{B,X}^n(Y) \tag{4}$$

where k is the number of iterations and $\delta_{B,X}^n$ is the conditional dilation applied 'n' times.

The images resulting from this reconstruction process were also subjected to the conditional dilation operator as presented in the following sections.

3.2 Length tests of linear structuring element

The first stage of the experiment focused on investigating the effect of the lengths of linear structuring elements in the conditional dilation operations, as well as the impact of dilation and erosion operations across the different tested spectral bands.

The results allowed the identification of both an optimal length of the linear structuring element for each specific band and the most suitable operator per band. It is important to note, however, that the definition of conditional dilation ($\delta_{B,X}$) involves a dilation operation followed by a comparison with the original image (or a subset). The use of erosion instead of dilation constitutes a variant of this definition (denoted here as $\delta'_{B,X}$) which does not conform to the standard definition of conditional dilation, nor to that of conditional erosion.

Figure 2 illustrates the evolution graphs of the *Intersection over Union* (IoU) and *F1-Score* metrics for the application of conditional dilation ($\delta_{B,X}$) using linear structuring elements (B) of varying lengths on Sentinel-2 bands b2, b3, b4, b8, NDBI, NDVI, and NDWI. As shown in Figure 2, for bands b2, b3, b4, NDBI, and NDWI, increasing the length of the linear structuring element (B) enhanced the highlighting of road axes, as reflected by improvements in the metric values. Conversely, increasing the length of the structuring element did not improve road enhancement in bands b8 and NDVI, with results tending to worsen.

Figure 2 - Percentage values of the IoU and F1-Score metrics for conditional dilation ($\delta_{B,X}$) using different structuring element lengths. (left) IoU metric (%); (right) F1-Score metric (%).

Figure 3 presents the evolution plots of the Intersection over Union (IoU) and F1-Score metrics for the application of the conditional dilation variant using the erosion operator ($\delta'_{B,X}$), with structuring elements (B) of varying lengths applied to Sentinel-2 bands b2, b3, b4, b8, NDBI, NDVI, and NDWI. In contrast to the results observed in the first conditional dilation test, Figure 3 shows that increasing the length of the linear structuring element (B) enhanced the delineation of road axes in bands b8 and NDVI, as indicated by higher metric values. On the other hand, in this test using the erosion operator, increasing the structuring element length did not improve road enhancement in bands b2, b3, b4, NDBI, and NDWI.

In summary, increasing the length of the linear structuring element enhanced road feature extraction in the images using the conditional dilation operator ($\delta_{B,X}$) for bands b2, b3, b4, NDBI, and NDWI, while it degraded performance for bands b8 and NDVI. On the other hand, in the tests with the conditional dilation variant using the erosion operator ($\delta'_{B,X}$), increasing B improved road enhancement in bands b8 and NDVI, but impaired it in the other bands. Therefore, it can be stated that increasing B tends to favor road enhancement in either the conditional dilation or its erosion-based variant.

Figure 3 - Percentage values of IoU and F1-Score metrics for the conditional dilation variant using the erosion operator ($\delta'_{B,X}$), considering different lengths of the structuring element: (left) IoU metric (%); (right) F1-Score metric (%).

Table 1 presents the structuring element lengths (B) that yielded the highest values of the IoU and F1-Score metrics for each spectral band in the tests conducted.

Table 1 – Best length values and corresponding metrics (IoU and F1-score) for each band, obtained using the conditional dilation operator ($\delta_{B,X}$) and its variant ($\delta'_{B,X}$).

Operation	Metric	b2	b3	b4	b8	NDVI	NDBI	NDWI
$\delta_{B,X}$	IoU	255	215	35	5	180	385	380
	F1-Score	255	215	35	5	180	385	380
$\delta'_{B,X}$	IoU	5	5	5	385	380	5	5
	F1-Score	5	5	5	385	380	5	5

Based on the data presented in Table 1, it is possible to define an average value of B that favors road enhancement across both configurations and all spectral bands, resulting in an approximate value of $B = 380$ pixels. This value does not cover the result obtained for band 4, where the best enhancement was achieved with a linear structuring element of $B = 35$ pixels using the conditional dilation operator ($\delta_{B,X}$). For the tests involving the conditional dilation variant ($\delta'_{B,X}$), bands b8 and NDVI yielded the best results across the evaluated metrics when the length of the linear structuring element was set to 385 and 380, respectively.

In summary, considering the two scenarios presented, defining the structuring element size as 380 is expected to benefit, on average, both bands b2, b3, b4, NDBI, and NDWI with the operator $\delta_{B,X}$, as well as bands b8 and NDVI with the operator $\delta'_{B,X}$.

3.3 Conditional dilation tests

Based on the tests assessing the influence of linear structuring element length and the determination of an average value of B that favors road enhancement across the studied bands, the main conditional dilation experiments were subsequently conducted.

These experiments aimed to evaluate the effect of two morphological operators: conditional dilation ($\delta_{B,X}$) and its variant using erosion instead of dilation ($\delta'_{B,X}$), applied to bands b2, b3, b4, b8, NDBI, NDVI and NDWI. Additionally, the same tests were performed on the images resulting from the application of the opening-by-reconstruction (OR) operator to these bands, defined by the Equation 4.

Following the experiments, the IoU and F1-Score metrics were computed for each resulting band/image, and their mean values were presented in graphical form.

Figure 4 presents boxplot graphs of the mean IoU for the morphological conditional dilation operator ($\delta_{B,X}$) applied to both the original images and those resulting from the opening-by-reconstruction process. The boxplot shows that the bands with the best performance for the operator ($\delta_{B,X}$) were b2, b3, NDBI, and NDWI. Additionally, the enhancement of road centerlines was slightly degraded in the images processed with the opening-by-reconstruction step, as indicated by slightly lower IoU values. In contrast, roads in bands b4, b8, and NDVI were barely enhanced by the conditional dilation operator. This same pattern is reflected by the mean F1-score for the bands.

Figure 5 presents boxplots of the mean IoU for the modified conditional dilation operator ($\delta'_{B,X}$) applied to the original images and those processed with the opening-by-reconstruction operator.

Figure 4 - Boxplot of the IoU metric for the conditional dilation operator ($\delta_{B,X}$) applied to original images (left) and images resulting from the opening-by-reconstruction process (right).

Figure 5 - Boxplot of the IoU metric for the modified conditional dilation operator ($\delta'_{B,X}$) applied to original images (left) and images resulting from the opening-by-reconstruction process (right).

From Figure 5, it can be observed that the best-performing bands for the operator ($\delta'_{B,X}$) were b8 and NDVI. Moreover, a subtle degradation in road centerline enhancement was noted for the images subjected to the opening-by-

reconstruction process, reflected by slightly lower IoU values. In contrast, roads in bands b2, b3, b4, NDBI and NDWI were barely enhanced using the modified conditional dilation operator.

Figure 6 illustrates the results of the conditional dilation operator ($\delta_{B,X}$) applied to all original bands and the corresponding bands processed with opening-by-reconstruction. Based on the visual analysis of the images, the best road axis enhancement was observed in the NDWI band, followed by NDBI and b2, which corresponds to the highest metric values shown in Figure 4.

Figure 7 presents the results of the modified conditional dilation operator ($\delta'_{B,X}$) applied to all original bands and their respective opening-by-reconstruction versions. Visual inspection reveals that the best enhancement of the road axis occurred in bands b8 and NDVI, corresponding to the best metrics observed in Figures 5.

3.4 Discussion

The results obtained illustrated the effects of the fundamental properties of the erosion and dilation operators. In images where the mean gray level of roads is relatively bright (bands b2, b3, NDBI, and NDWI), the use of the dilation operator favored their detection. Conversely, in images where the road gray level is darker (bands b8 and NDVI), the erosion operator provided greater enhancement.

Quantitative comparison of the results was facilitated by calculating the IoU and F1-score metrics, enabled by the creation of binary masks representing road centerlines, which allowed direct comparison with the output images produced by the morphological operators.

Regarding the length of the linear structuring element, a value of 380 pixels achieved the best compromise across all tested bands, with the exception of band b4, which did not exhibit significant improvements in any of the tested scenarios. It consistently showed lower average performance compared to the other bands, as reflected both visually and by the IoU and F1-score metrics. Future tests involving this band may benefit from using a smaller structuring element (approximately 34 pixels).

Overall, the conditional dilation operator ($\delta_{B,X}$) applied to NDWI and NDBI images effectively enhanced and delineated most of the road axes present in the scenes. Likewise, the modified operator variant ($\delta'_{B,X}$) performed satisfactorily for bands b8 and NDVI, highlighting road axes more effectively than in other bands.

However, despite the sequence of applied operators satisfactorily extracting road axes in the abovementioned bands, a number of non-road objects were also enhanced. This is reflected in the relatively low values of the IoU and F1-score metrics: although most road axes were detected, the increase in false positives degraded the final metric values. It is noteworthy that water bodies and other human-made structures were also sharply highlighted. This outcome is related to the characteristics of the indices used (NDWI and NDBI), which are designed to emphasize water bodies and built-up objects in the scenes, respectively. Additionally, a characteristic of morphological operators is that they do not consider the radiometric values of the objects present in the images, which contributes to the high incidence of false positives in the images.

Finally, it is worth noting that applying the opening-by-reconstruction operator prior to conditional dilation had little impact on the overall quality of the results. For some bands, a slight degradation in road centerline detection was observed, as reflected in reduced IoU and F1-score values. This suggests that the use of eroded images as markers for road centerlines was not sufficiently effective, underscoring the need for more accurate axis identification when selecting markers.

4 CONCLUSION

The presented experiment consisted of applying the conditional dilation operator composed of a linear structuring element B in different orientations to Sentinel-2 bands b2, b3, b4, and b8, as well as to the NDVI, NDBI, and NDWI index images derived from these bands. A dedicated dataset was created for this experiment, comprising approximately 890 image patches for each band.

The conditional dilation operator, along with a variant using the erosion operator instead of dilation, was applied both directly to the dataset images and to the results of the opening-by-reconstruction operator applied across all bands. The results demonstrated the feasibility of the experiment for enhancing road centerlines, particularly in the NDBI and NDWI bands. Furthermore, the optimal size of the linear structuring element B for enhancing road centerlines in Sentinel-2 imagery was investigated. A value of 380 pixels was adopted in order to achieve improved results across the widest range of tested bands.

In this context, future work could explore the application of additional morphological operators alongside conditional dilation, aiming to combine the results from different bands/images and improve the ability to detect road axes.

Finally, further experiments combining the results of the conditional dilation operator with the goal of extracting more distinctive road features in binary images may improve the overall result quality. Likewise, the use of the opening-by-reconstruction operator with more specific markers is recommended to enhance performance.

Figure 6 - Conditional dilation operator ($\delta_{B,X}$) applied to original bands and their respective opening-by-reconstruction versions from Sentinel-2 imagery. From left to right: Original image, Binary result from conditional dilation, Binary result from conditional dilation applied to the opening-by-reconstruction image, Ground truth binary mask.

Figure 7 - Modified conditional dilation operator ($\delta'_{B,X}$) applied to original bands and their respective opening-by-reconstruction versions. From left to right: Original image, Binary result from conditional dilation, Binary result from conditional dilation applied to the opening-by-reconstruction image, Ground truth binary mask.

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